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Title: The effect of a 5-day course of azithromycin on *Streptococcus pneumoniae* carriage and antimicrobial resistance among Kenyan children discharged from hospital

Authors: Tanya E. Libby, PhD¹, Angela Karani, MA², Kirkby D. Tickell, PhD³, Donald Akech, BSc², Benson Singa, MPH⁴, Doreen Rwigyira⁴, Kevin Kariuki, MS⁴, Nancy Onamu⁴, Derrick Ounga⁴, James A. Berkley, MD^{2,5}, Judd L. Walson, MD^{3,6}, J. Anthony G. Scott, DTMH^{2,7}, Patricia B. Pavlinac, PhD³

Affiliations:

¹University of Washington, Department of Epidemiology, Seattle, WA, USA

²Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI)-Wellcome Trust Research Programme, Kilifi, Kenya

³University of Washington, Department of Global Health, Seattle, WA, USA

⁴Kenya Medical Research Institute, Nairobi, Kenya

⁵University of Oxford, Centre for Tropical Medicine & Global Health, Oxford, UK

⁶Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Baltimore, MD

⁷London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine, Department of Infectious Disease Epidemiology, London, UK

Corresponding author:

Tanya Libby, MPH, PhD,

University of Washington, Department of Epidemiology

Seattle, WA, USA

Email: Libbyte@uw.edu

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Summary: Among children discharged from hospital in Kenya, a 5-day course of azithromycin compared to placebo did not affect pneumococcal carriage or antimicrobial resistance 3- or 6-months post-randomization.

Abstract

Background: Mass azithromycin distribution reduces child mortality in some settings, potentially through reductions in nasopharyngeal carriage of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, but has been associated with increased antimicrobial resistance. Individual-level data are lacking on the impact of azithromycin on antimicrobial resistance over time.

Methods: We analyzed data from a double-blind, randomized placebo-controlled trial (ClinicalTrials.gov; NCT02414399) which followed 1,398 hospitalized Kenyan children to evaluate the impact of a 5-day course of oral azithromycin at discharge from hospital on pneumococcal carriage and the proportion of isolates (among a random sample) resistant to azithromycin. Randomization to azithromycin or placebo (1:1) was stratified by enrollment county (Kisii or Homa Bay). Using generalized estimating equations, we calculated prevalence ratios (PRs) and 95% confidence intervals for the intervention, adjusting for enrollment site.

Results: Overall, 1,253/1398 (89.6%) enrolled children received antibiotics during their hospitalization. Pneumococcal carriage at discharge was similar among children randomized to the azithromycin group (158/702 [22.5%]) compared to the placebo group (171/696 [24.6%]; $p=0.4$) and did not differ at month 3 (65.6% vs 67.0%; PR:0.98[0.90, 1.06]) or month 6 (66.7% vs 66.5%; PR:1.00[0.92, 1.08]). At discharge, 15.7% of isolates were resistant to azithromycin and there was no difference between azithromycin-treated and placebo groups at month 3 (35/266 [13.2%] vs 32/256 [12.5%]; PR:1.06[0.86, 1.66]) or month 6 (41/245 [16.7%] vs 43/243 [17.6%]; PR:1.01[0.69,1.49]).

Conclusions: Azithromycin treatment did not effect pneumococcal carriage or antimicrobial resistance 3- or 6-months post-randomization. High inpatient antibiotic use in this recently discharged population may have reduced any further impact of azithromycin.

Keywords: *Streptococcus pneumoniae*; azithromycin; pneumococcus; Kenya; antimicrobial resistance; children

Background

More than 2.8 million deaths occur each year among children under five years of age in sub-Saharan Africa,¹ primarily due to preventable and treatable infectious conditions, most commonly pneumonia.² Children who survive hospitalization continue to experience an elevated risk of death, with mortality rates averaging 3-5% in the 6 months following hospitalization.^{3,4} This elevated risk may arise from inadequate treatment of the acute presenting condition, nosocomial infections, untreated underlying conditions, and/or alterations to the bacterial flora of the gut and nasopharynx.

Mass drug administration (MDA) of azithromycin to all young children in a community is being considered as a mortality-preventing intervention in some high-mortality settings following promising results seen from trials conducted in Ethiopia and Niger.⁵⁻⁷ However, guidance from the World Health Organization for the mass use of azithromycin for mortality prevention is limited due to concerns about promotion of antimicrobial resistance (AMR).⁸ Azithromycin MDA has been associated with an increase in azithromycin resistance in commensal bacteria, including *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, the leading bacterial cause of pneumonia.^{9,10} Limited evidence suggests repeated MDA rounds may increase resistance to non-macrolide antibiotics, such as beta-lactams, which are first-line therapy for pneumococcal pneumonia.¹¹ Existing data on the effect of MDA programs on *S. pneumoniae* are limited to cross-sectional population-level surveys. There is a lack of individual-level longitudinal data on the trajectory of resistance in *S. pneumoniae* among children treated with azithromycin.

As an alternative to MDA, targeted use of azithromycin among children at highest risk of mortality, such as those recently discharged from the hospital, may reduce mortality while minimizing population-wide development of resistance. We previously reported results from a randomized, placebo-controlled trial¹² evaluating the effect of a 5-day course of azithromycin on risk of rehospitalization and death among Kenyan children recently discharged from the hospital. The intervention was not found to reduce re-hospitalization and mortality in this population.¹³ Here, we investigate whether nasopharyngeal carriage of *S. pneumoniae* and resistance to azithromycin and other relevant antimicrobial classes varied by azithromycin treatment arm at 3- and 6-months post-discharge. We hypothesized that five days of azithromycin may lower the prevalence of *S. pneumoniae* carriage in the short term and select for azithromycin-resistant strains of *S. pneumoniae*, resulting in a higher proportion of carried isolates that are resistant. From a public health perspective, we sought to determine whether any difference in resistant carriage was

sustained for 3 to 6 months. A better understanding of AMR in azithromycin-treated children could inform the rollout of MDA programs.

Methods

Study design and population

We conducted a longitudinal analysis using data collected from children enrolled in a double-blind, placebo-controlled, randomized clinical trial called Toto Bora (registered at ClinicalTrials.gov; NCT02414399).¹² The trial received ethical approval from the Institutional Review Boards of the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI SERU #3086), the Kenyan Pharmacy and Poisons Board (Ref. No. PPB/ECCT/15/10/04), and the University of Washington (IRB #49120). Written informed consent was obtained from all participating caregivers in their preferred language (English, Kiswahili, Kisii, or Luo). For individuals who were not literate, the consent form was read aloud in their preferred language, and consent was documented using a thumbprint in the presence of a witness.

The trial enrolled children 1-59 months of age, admitted to the hospital for non-traumatic conditions from June 2016–November 2019 and subsequently discharged, with weight >2 kilograms and plans to remain in the study area for at least 6 months. Details of the trial protocol and statistical analysis plan have been published.^{12,13} Recruitment was completed in the inpatient wards of Kisii Regional and Homa Bay District Hospitals in [formerly] Nyanza Province in western Kenya, a low-resource setting where the under-five mortality rate was estimated to be 55.7 per 1,000 live births in 2022.¹⁴ Randomization to the azithromycin or placebo arm (1:1) in blocks of 10 was stratified by enrollment site (Kisii or Homa Bay).

AMR sub-study: A random sample of 844 children from the parent trial was selected for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST). To maintain randomization, the sample was drawn irrespective of whether *S. pneumoniae* was isolated at a given time point. The final sample size of the AMR sub-study was selected to achieve a target of at least 1,200 *S. pneumoniae* isolates for AST testing across three time points.

Data collection

Caregivers of enrolled children were interviewed to collect medical history and sociodemographic information, including household characteristics and environmental exposures. Hospital records were abstracted to ascertain clinical history, diagnoses, antibiotic use, and laboratory data. At 3-

and 6-month follow-up visits, caregivers were interviewed about any illnesses, re-hospitalizations, or treatments given to the child, and about study drug adherence at the 3-month visit. Child anthropometric measurements were collected at enrollment and 3- and 6-month follow-up visits. Vaccination history was determined by immunization record when available and supplemented by caregiver self-report. If a participant failed to return for a scheduled follow-up visit, study staff attempted to make contact via cellphone with primary caregivers, and then followed up via a home visit. Participants were considered lost to follow-up if they did not attend either follow-up visit despite one month of active tracing.

Nasopharyngeal swabs (Copan Diagnostics, USA), the gold standard method for measuring pneumococcal carriage in children,¹⁵ were collected from all children at enrollment (post-discharge, before administration of study medication) and from all surviving children at 3- and 6-month follow-up visits. Swabs were immediately placed in skim milk, tryptone, glucose, and glycerin (STGG) media, vortexed to make a back-up sample, and frozen within 1 hour of collection, in onsite -80°C freezers with generator and solar-power back-up, and then shipped, on dry ice, monthly to the Kenya Medical Research Institute (KEMRI) in Nairobi for long-term -80°C storage.

Nasopharyngeal culture was done on all available swab samples (baseline, 3-months, and 6-months) on blood agar with gentamicin, and all suspected *S. pneumoniae* colonies were confirmed by optochin test at the KEMRI-Wellcome Trust Research Programme laboratory in Kilifi, Kenya following established protocols.¹⁵ For children randomly selected for the AMR sub-study, one *S. pneumoniae* isolate per child from all available timepoints underwent AST with the disc diffusion method for azithromycin, oxacillin (for penicillin susceptibility), doxycycline, levofloxacin, co-trimoxazole, chloramphenicol, clindamycin, and linezolid and by E-TEST for ceftriaxone. Isolates were classified as susceptible, intermediate, or resistant according to 2024 Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) zone diameter breakpoints or minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) breakpoints for ceftriaxone.¹⁶ Intermediate and resistant isolates were considered non-susceptible.

Intervention

After hospital discharge and baseline sample collection, enrolled children received the first daily dose of either oral suspension azithromycin (10mg/kg) or a similar appearing placebo under observation by study staff. The subsequent four doses (5mg/kg azithromycin or placebo) were administered daily by caregivers at home.

Outcomes

The primary outcomes were a) the prevalence of *S. pneumoniae* carriage, defined as the proportion of children with microbiological isolation of *S. pneumoniae* from a nasopharyngeal swab, and b) the proportion of carried pneumococci that were resistant to azithromycin at baseline (discharge) and 3- and 6-month follow-up visits. Secondary outcomes included the proportion of carried pneumococci that were resistant to other classes of antimicrobials and that were multidrug-resistant (MDR) defined as non-susceptible to three or more antimicrobial classes tested.

Statistical analysis

Given the sample size from the parent trial (N=1400) and assuming alpha 0.05 and 67% carriage in placebo-treated children, we were powered to detect an 11% reduction in carriage (prevalence ratio of 0.89) associated with the azithromycin treatment. Among the AMR sub-study (N=844), we expected approximately 280 *S. pneumoniae* isolates in each arm at each follow-up visit. Assuming an alpha level of 0.05 and 15% of isolates resistant to azithromycin in the placebo group, we had 80% power to detect a 57% increase in the proportion of isolates that were resistant, which is comparable to prevalence ratios ranging from 1.6 to 2.3 in MDA trials for mortality prevention.¹⁷

For each outcome, we compared the prevalence of *S. pneumoniae* carriage or the proportion of isolates that were antimicrobial resistant in the intervention vs. control groups. First, we conducted an unadjusted analysis comparing the prevalence in the two groups using a z-test. Next, we performed an adjusted individual-level analysis using generalized estimating equations (GEE) with a Poisson link function, an exchangeable correlation structure to account for correlation within individuals over time, and stratification by enrollment site (via adjustment). Our primary analysis was intention-to-treat (ITT), adjusting only for enrollment site. In per-protocol analyses, we included only participants who self-reported full adherence to the 5-day course of azithromycin. We calculated prevalence ratios and 95% confidence intervals (CI) for *S. pneumoniae* carriage associated with the intervention. To assess changes over time, we included an interaction term between follow-up visit and the intervention. In sensitivity analyses, we adjusted for factors known to be strongly predictive of *S. pneumoniae* carriage, including age, nutritional status, exclusive breastfeeding for the first six months of life, HIV status, living in a crowded household (>3 persons/room), and *S. pneumoniae* status at baseline.

We assessed effect modification on the multiplicative scale by baseline *S. pneumoniae* status (carriage/non-carriage) and by antibiotic use during the initial hospitalization (any/none). We conducted a pre-specified subgroup analysis stratified by enrollment site. We conducted two-tailed tests with alpha 0.05. All analyses were completed with R version 4.0.3.

Results

From June 2016–November 2019, 1,400 children were enrolled in the Toto Bora trial; two were deemed ineligible after randomization. Baseline characteristics of the 1,398 children included in the ITT analysis are summarized in table 1. The median age was 18 months (IQR 9-32), median duration of hospitalization was 3 days (IQR 2-5), and 1,253/1398 (89.6%) children received antibiotics during their hospitalization, most commonly penicillin (60%) and gentamicin (54%). Over 93% of children were up to date on pneumococcal conjugate vaccine (PCV) doses for their age: 561/604 (92.9%) among those with vaccination cards and 735/788 (93.3%) among those without (based on caregiver-report). Overall, 1324 (95.1%) received at least one dose of PCV10 (GlaxoSmithKline), 1304 (93.7%) two doses, and 1246 (89.5%) three doses. Participant characteristics were generally balanced between the azithromycin and placebo arms, except for slightly more children in the azithromycin group being partly (rather than exclusively) breastfed and slightly more children in the azithromycin group living in crowded households.

The first dose of azithromycin or placebo was given under observation for all children and 658/691 (95.2%) in the azithromycin group and 653/682 (95.7%) in the placebo group received all five doses of the study drug as reported by caregivers. Non-study use of azithromycin during follow-up was reported for 3/1398 (0.2%) participants; two in the placebo arm and one in the azithromycin treatment arm. During the 6-month follow-up, 132 (9.4%) children experienced the combined outcome of death or rehospitalization; 34 (2.4%) children died and 115 (8.2%) were rehospitalized at least once.

S. pneumoniae carriage

Nasopharyngeal swabs were available for testing for 1395/1398 (99.8%) children at baseline, 1255 (89.8%) at month 3, and 1201 (85.9%) at month 6. Baseline carriage of *S. pneumoniae* was similar among children randomized to the azithromycin group (158/701 [22.5%]) compared to the placebo group (171/694 [24.6%]) (p=0.4).

In ITT analysis, adjusting for enrollment site, azithromycin treatment compared to placebo was not associated with carriage of *S. pneumoniae* at 3 months (420/640 [65.6%] vs 412/615 [67.0%]);

PR 0.98 [95% CI 0.90, 1.06]) or 6 months (405/607 [66.7%] vs 395/594 [66.5%]; PR 1.00 [0.92, 1.08]) (figure 1). There was low within-person correlation for *S. pneumoniae* carriage in our model ($\alpha=0.170$; standard error=0.017), as shown in the figure of individual trajectories (appendix, figure S1). There was no evidence for a change in the effect of the intervention over time ($p=0.51$). While baseline *S. pneumoniae*, age, breastfeeding in the first 6 months of life, and household crowding were predictors of later colonization, including them in the model did not change the point estimate or standard error for the effect of the intervention (appendix table S1).

The baseline prevalence of carriage was higher among children who did not receive any inpatient antibiotics (41/74 [55.4%] azithromycin-treated children and 33/70 [47.1%] placebo-treated children). However, neither baseline carriage (interaction $p=0.52$) nor inpatient antibiotic use ($p=0.16$) modified the treatment effect (appendix, figure S2). We did not observe a difference between enrollment sites in baseline carriage of *S. pneumoniae* or in the effect of the intervention on carriage (appendix, figure S3).

Antimicrobial resistance

The 844 children (429 azithromycin-treated and 415 placebo-treated) randomly selected for the AMR sub-study were representative of the overall trial participants in terms of baseline characteristics and *S. pneumoniae* prevalence (appendix, table S2). *S. pneumoniae* was isolated and AST testing completed for 1220 nasopharyngeal swabs collected from these children across the three timepoints (210 isolates at baseline, 522 at month 3, and 488 at month 6). AST results at baseline (prior to randomization) are summarized in table 2 and appendix figures S4, S5; 34.8% (73/210) of isolates were resistant to 3 or more antimicrobial classes.

Comparing azithromycin and placebo arms, the percent of isolates resistant to azithromycin did not differ at month 3 (35/266 [13.2%] vs 32/256 [12.5%]; PR 1.06 [0.86, 1.66]) or month 6 (41/245 [16.7%] vs 43/243 [17.6%]; PR 1.01 [0.69, 1.49]) (figure 2). Results were similar when adjusting for baseline *S. pneumoniae*, breastfeeding, and household crowding. In per-protocol analyses, results did not meaningfully differ when children who did not complete the full 5-day course were excluded (appendix, table S3).

Baseline carriage did not modify the effect of the intervention on azithromycin-resistance among *S. pneumoniae* isolates ($p=0.38$). There was some evidence that the effect of the intervention on azithromycin resistance varied by antibiotic use during the enrollment hospitalization ($p=0.053$; appendix, figure S6). However, among the subset of children that did not receive any inpatient

antibiotics, we observed imbalance in the proportion of isolates that were resistant to azithromycin in the two treatment arms at baseline (prior to randomization), likely due to the small sample size (appendix, table S4). Therefore, we performed a post-hoc analysis among this subset of children, adjusting for baseline resistance to azithromycin, and found the intervention to be associated with a higher proportion of azithromycin resistance at 6 months (PR 5.4 [1.53, 19.1]) and not significantly so at 3 months (PR 1.33 [0.31, 5.66]) (appendix, table S4). While the proportion of azithromycin-resistant pneumococci was higher in Homa Bay compared to Kisii at baseline (PR 1.63 [1.20, 2.20]; $p=0.002$), we did not observe an effect of county on the relationship between the intervention and azithromycin resistance ($p=0.85$; appendix, figure S7).

We did not observe a difference between treatment arms in the proportion of carried pneumococci resistant to penicillin (via oxacillin), doxycycline, or clindamycin, or in the proportion of isolates that were MDR (figure 3). We did not have sufficient resistant isolates to examine treatment effects for resistance to ceftriaxone, chloramphenicol, or linezolid.

Discussion

In this randomized, double-blind clinical trial, we did not find evidence of an effect of a 5-day course of azithromycin prescribed at hospital discharge on the prevalence of pneumococcal carriage or the proportion of carried *S. pneumoniae* that were antimicrobial resistant at 3- or 6-months post-discharge. Both treatment arms had similar carriage prevalence at baseline, therefore, adjusting for baseline pneumococcal carriage did not affect the prevalence ratios at outcome nor did baseline carriage prevalence modify the effect of azithromycin on carriage prevalence. The lack of an effect on *S. pneumoniae* carriage is consistent with findings from MDA trials of azithromycin for mortality prevention, which found no difference in the prevalence of carriage among children in azithromycin communities compared to control.^{9,17,18} However, our AMR findings differ from the MORDOR (Macrolides Oraux pour Réduire les Décès avec un Oeil sur la Résistance) I trial, which found children living in azithromycin MDA communities in Niger and Malawi had 9.4% and 11.1% higher proportion, respectively, of azithromycin resistance among carried *S. pneumoniae* isolates 6 months after the fourth treatment round.^{9,17,19} Of note, the MORDOR trial was conducted in community settings, which differ from the population of hospitalized children included here.

The lack of an observed effect of the azithromycin intervention on resistance in *S. pneumoniae* to azithromycin was unexpected but is encouraging. In contrast to the single dose of azithromycin used in most MDA programs, the five-day course of azithromycin may have effectively killed all

present *S. pneumoniae* rather than selecting for resistant clones. Our sub-study was powered to detect an 8% absolute difference in the proportion of carried isolates that were resistant, so we cannot rule out the possibility of a smaller intervention effect, though the observed 1% differences are unlikely to be meaningful. There are other possible explanations for these findings. First, a transient increase in azithromycin resistance may have occurred prior to the collection of nasopharyngeal swabs at the 3-month follow-up visit. This interval was selected from a public health perspective, but may have been too long to assess an impact of azithromycin treatment due to high turnover of carried pneumococcal strains. While azithromycin has an extended half-life (2-4 days),²⁰ selective pressure would begin to wane several days after the last dose. Given an estimated mean carriage duration of 31 days and an acquisition rate of 6% per day,²¹ most children would have reacquired pneumococcal strains during follow-up that were representative of resistance levels in their community. Lastly, the high rate of inpatient antibiotic use and exposure to resistant bacteria during hospitalization may have minimized the remaining potential effect of the intervention in this population.²² Indeed, when we examined the effect among children without inpatient antibiotic exposure (who had a higher prevalence of *S. pneumoniae* at baseline), there was a moderate signal for increasing azithromycin resistance in the azithromycin-treated group compared to placebo.

Overall, the prevalence of carriage of *S. pneumoniae* nearly tripled from hospital discharge to 6-month follow-up. The relatively low prevalence of carriage post-discharge is consistent with prior research showing reductions following antibiotic use,²³ as 90% of participants had at least one antibiotic during their hospitalization. The lack of an effect of the azithromycin intervention on *S. pneumoniae* carriage is consistent with previous studies which found no reduction in carriage or a transient reduction for one month.²⁴

At hospital discharge, nearly all isolates tested were resistant to at least one antimicrobial, and nearly 35% were resistant to three or more antimicrobial classes. We observed high levels of non-susceptibility to oxacillin, which is likely a reflection of the level of inpatient penicillin exposure in this population. Recent hospitalization is a risk factor for Beta-lactam and macrolide resistance in *S. pneumoniae*.²² The relatively high proportion of resistance at discharge to antimicrobials which are not commonly used in the study population (e.g., doxycycline and azithromycin) may be attributed to co-selection pressure mediated by other antibiotics such as cephalosporins.²⁵ The proportion of isolates resistant to azithromycin was similar to that seen in cross-sectional surveys in Asembo (12%) and lower than that observed in Kibera (24%).²⁶ Of note, azithromycin resistance was lower in *S. pneumoniae* compared to commensal *E. coli* isolated from our study

participants at baseline (37.7% resistant; data previously published).¹³ This may be related to the high bacterial diversity, selective pressure within the gut, mobile genetic element exchange between Gram negative species, and longer exposure time to oral antimicrobials.

Strengths of this study include longitudinal follow-up, the large sample of nasopharyngeal swabs tested, AST of nine antimicrobial classes, high adherence to the intervention (including 100% adherence to the first dose), high participant retention (>99%), and a well-characterized study population. This work is also subject to several limitations. We were underpowered for the observed prevalence ratios, however, they were notably small, suggesting that if a true difference exists, it is unlikely to be impactful. Given the high rate of *S. pneumoniae* acquisition in this population, a shorter interval (e.g., 2-4 weeks) to the first swab collection may have increased the likelihood of observing an intervention effect. Adherence to the trial medication was assessed by caregiver report, which may have overestimated the true adherence. There was potential for non-study azithromycin use, however, we expect this was rare based on data collected at follow-up visits and data from the MAL-ED cohort from Tanzania and South Africa, suggesting macrolide use in the region is rare.²⁷ Serotyping data for *S. pneumoniae* were not available, which limits our ability to distinguish between new and continued colonization. While less than 3% of participants died during follow-up, survival bias may be a concern if *S. pneumoniae* carriage and AMR profiles differed for children who survived until follow-up visits. Finally, because our study population is limited to recently hospitalized children, these results are not generalizable to the community.

In summary, among Kenyan children recently discharged from the hospital, a 5-day course of azithromycin did not affect carriage of *S. pneumoniae* or resistance to azithromycin and other antimicrobials as measured 3- or 6-months post-discharge. This study suggests that any short-term impact of the azithromycin intervention on the resistance profile of carried *S. pneumoniae* is unlikely to last up to three months, at least in the context of settings where community azithromycin use is low. Surveillance for antimicrobial resistance remains a high priority, especially in settings with widespread use of antimicrobials in the community.

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Data sharing

Study protocol, informed consent forms, statistical analysis plan, and case report forms have been previously published (available: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(21\)00347-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(21)00347-8)). The de-identified dataset is available at:

<https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/YTMFOJ>.

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Tables and Figures

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of children enrolled in Toto Bora by randomization arm (n=1398)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 1,398 ¹	Azithromycin, N = 702 ¹	Placebo, N = 696 ¹
County of recruiting hospital			
Homa Bay	576 (41%)	290 (41%)	286 (41%)
Kisii	822 (59%)	412 (59%)	410 (59%)
Age (months)	18 (9, 32)	18 (9, 31)	18 (9, 33)
Age category (months)			
0-5	188 (13%)	94 (13%)	94 (14%)
6-11	277 (20%)	141 (20%)	136 (20%)
12-23	406 (29%)	202 (29%)	204 (29%)
24-59	527 (38%)	265 (38%)	262 (38%)
Sex			
Male	828 (59%)	426 (61%)	402 (58%)
Female	570 (41%)	276 (39%)	294 (42%)
Caregiver reported income			
≥5,000 KSh	454 (32%)	229 (33%)	225 (32%)
<5000 KSh	874 (63%)	433 (62%)	441 (63%)
Refused/unknown	70 (5.0%)	40 (5.7%)	30 (4.3%)
Highest level of education completed by primary caregiver			
Secondary school or greater	752 (54%)	368 (52%)	384 (55%)
Primary school or less	644 (46%)	333 (48%)	311 (45%)
Household crowding			
<3 persons per room	1,127 (81%)	559 (80%)	568 (82%)
≥3 persons per room	271 (19%)	143 (20%)	128 (18%)
Water source			
Improved	1,154 (83%)	577 (82%)	577 (83%)
Unimproved	243 (17%)	125 (18%)	118 (17%)
Type of toilet used by the household			
Flush	135 (9.7%)	74 (11%)	61 (8.8%)
Pit latrine	1,209 (87%)	599 (85%)	610 (88%)
Other (e.g., bush)	53 (3.8%)	28 (4.0%)	25 (3.6%)
Breastfeeding for first 6 months of life (or until enrollment if child <6 m)			
Never breastfed	24 (1.7%)	14 (2.0%)	10 (1.4%)
Exclusively breastfed	663 (47%)	322 (46%)	341 (49%)
Partially breastfed	632 (45%)	334 (48%)	298 (43%)
Unknown	79 (5.7%)	32 (4.6%)	47 (6.8%)
Acute malnutrition ²			
None	1,266 (91%)	638 (91%)	628 (90%)
Moderate	75 (5.4%)	36 (5.1%)	39 (5.6%)
Severe	57 (4.1%)	28 (4.0%)	29 (4.2%)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 1,398 ¹	Azithromycin, N = 702 ¹	Placebo, N = 696 ¹
Child HIV status			
HIV unexposed	1,192 (85%)	597 (85%)	595 (85%)
HIV exposed, uninfected	140 (10%)	70 (10%)	70 (10%)
HIV infected	18 (1.3%)	9 (1.3%)	9 (1.3%)
HIV uninfected, exposure status unknown	41 (2.9%)	23 (3.3%)	18 (2.6%)
HIV exposed, infection status unknown	7 (0.5%)	3 (0.4%)	4 (0.6%)
Has recommended number of PCV doses for this age (with grace of 4 weeks) ³	1,296 (93%)	651 (93%)	645 (93%)
Any antibiotic used during admission	1,253 (90%)	628 (89%)	625 (90%)
Penicillin	839 (60%)	417 (59%)	422 (61%)
Gentamicin	757 (54%)	375 (53%)	382 (55%)
Ceftriaxone	538 (39%)	270 (38%)	268 (39%)
Macrolides	52 (3.7%)	28 (4.0%)	26 (3.7%)
Any antibiotic prescribed at discharge	867 (62%)	447 (64%)	420 (60%)
<i>S. pneumoniae</i> detected at baseline	329 (24%)	158 (23%)	171 (25%)

KSh, Kenyan Shilling; PCV, pneumococcal conjugate vaccine

¹n(%), median (IQR)

² Moderate defined as weight-for-height Z score (WHZ) ≥ -3 to < -2 or mid-upper arm circumference (MUAC) ≥ 11.5 to < 12.5 cm; Severe defined as WHZ < -3 or MUAC < 11.5 or edema; MUAC only used among children aged 6 months or older

³Based on Kenya Ministry of Health vaccine schedule (allowing a 4-week window) recommending PCV-10 at 6, 10, and 14 weeks of age. The GlaxoSmithKline vaccine containing serotypes 1, 4, 5, 6B, 7F, 9V, 14, 18C, 19F, and 23F was exclusively used in this population.

Table 2. Proportion of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistant to each antimicrobial at baseline (n=210)

Antimicrobial	N	%
Co-trimoxazole	205	97.6%
Penicillin ¹	198	94.3%
Doxycycline	68	32.4%
Azithromycin	33	15.7%
Clindamycin	22	10.5%
Chloramphenicol	1	0.5%
Linezolid	1	0.5%
Levofloxacin	0	0%
Ceftriaxone ²	0	0%

Based on 2024 Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) disc diffusion zone diameter breakpoints or minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) breakpoints for ceftriaxone. Intermediate and resistant isolates were considered non-susceptible.

¹Represents non-susceptibility via Oxacillin disc diffusion test

²Based on non-meningitis MIC breakpoints

Figure titles and captions:

Figure 1. Percentage of swabs positive for *S. pneumoniae* by treatment arm

Caption: Error bars are 95% confidence intervals. The p-values are from a generalized estimating equation model with time by intervention interaction, adjusting for enrollment site.

There was no evidence that the difference between treatment arms changes over time (p=0.51).

The prevalence of carriage significantly increased from enrollment to month 3 (p<0.001).

ALT TEXT: Chart depicting the percentage of swabs positive for *S. pneumoniae* at enrollment, 3-, and 6-months by azithromycin treatment group, showing no difference between groups.

Figure 2. Percentage of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistance to azithromycin by treatment arm

Caption: Error bars are 95% confidence intervals. The p-values are from a generalized estimating equation model with time by intervention interaction, adjusting for enrollment site.

ALT TEXT: Chart depicting the percentage of *S. pneumoniae* isolates that were resistant to azithromycin at enrollment, 3-, and 6-months by azithromycin treatment group, showing no difference between groups.

Figure 3. Percentage of isolates resistant to other antimicrobials by treatment arm

Caption: Error bars are 95% confidence intervals.

ALT TEXT: A series of four charts depicting the percentage of *S. pneumoniae* isolates that were resistant to oxacillin, doxycycline, clindamycin, and multi-drug resistant at enrollment, 3-, and 6-months by azithromycin treatment group, showing no difference between groups.

Supplementary Appendix

The effect of a 5-day course of azithromycin on *Streptococcus pneumoniae* carriage and antimicrobial resistance among Kenyan children discharged from the hospital

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Figure S1. Trajectory of *S. pneumoniae* carriage and azithromycin resistance over the 6 months post-discharge by treatment arm (n=844 children)

Table S1. Effect of azithromycin intervention on *S. pneumoniae* carriage at 3- and 6-month follow-up using generalized estimating equations, adjusting for county of enrollment and predictors of *S. pneumoniae* carriage

Characteristic	Model 1			Model 2		
	PR	95% CI	p-value	PR	95% CI	p-value
Azithromycin (vs. placebo)	1.00	0.94, 1.06	0.88	0.99	0.93, 1.05	0.632
County of enrollment						
Homa Bay	REF	—	—	REF	—	—
Kisii	0.97	0.91, 1.03	0.34	0.96	0.89, 1.02	0.177
<i>S. pneumoniae</i> at baseline	1.30	1.22, 1.38	<0.001	1.26	1.19, 1.34	<0.001
Age at enrollment (months)						
0-5				1.19	1.08, 1.31	<0.001
6-11				1.19	1.09, 1.30	<0.001
12-23				1.13	1.05, 1.23	0.002
24-59				REF		
Breastfeeding in the first 6 months of life						
Exclusively breastfed				REF	—	—
Never breastfed				1.01	0.82, 1.24	0.923
Partially breastfed				1.09	1.02, 1.17	0.010
Unknown				0.84	0.71, 1.00	0.053
Household crowding (>=3 persons per room) at enrollment				1.08	1.01, 1.16	0.035

PR = Prevalence Ratio, CI = Confidence Interval;

Model 1 is adjusted for county of enrollment and *S. pneumoniae* at baseline

Model 2 is adjusted for county of enrollment and *S. pneumoniae* at baseline, age category, breastfeeding status, and household crowding.

Figure S2. The effect of azithromycin on the percentage of swabs positive for *S. pneumoniae*, stratified by whether the child received any antibiotics during their hospitalization

Figure S3. The effect of azithromycin on percentage of swabs positive for *S. pneumoniae*, stratified by enrollment county

Table S2. Characteristics of children randomly selected for antimicrobial susceptibility testing (AST)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 1,398 ¹	AST Sample, N = 844 ¹	Not Sampled, N = 554 ¹
Randomization arm			
Placebo	696 (50%)	415 (49%)	281 (51%)
AZM	702 (50%)	429 (51%)	273 (49%)
County of recruiting hospital			
Homa Bay	576 (41%)	337 (40%)	239 (43%)
Kisii	822 (59%)	507 (60%)	315 (57%)
Age at enrollment (months)	18 (9, 32)	18 (9, 32)	18 (9, 32)
Child age category (months)			
0-5 mo	188 (13%)	109 (13%)	79 (14%)
6-11 mo	277 (20%)	168 (20%)	109 (20%)
12-23 mo	406 (29%)	250 (30%)	156 (28%)
24-59 mo	527 (38%)	317 (38%)	210 (38%)
Sex			
Male	828 (59%)	495 (59%)	333 (60%)
Female	570 (41%)	349 (41%)	221 (40%)
Caregiver reported income			
Income \geq 5000 ksh	454 (32%)	267 (32%)	187 (34%)
Income < 5000 ksh	874 (63%)	535 (63%)	339 (61%)
Unknown or refuse to answer	70 (5.0%)	42 (5.0%)	28 (5.1%)
Highest level of education completed by primary caregiver			
Secondary or greater	752 (54%)	450 (53%)	302 (55%)
Primary school or less	644 (46%)	394 (47%)	250 (45%)
Household crowding			
No crowding (< 3 persons per room)	1,127 (81%)	684 (81%)	443 (80%)
Crowding (\geq 3 persons per room)	271 (19%)	160 (19%)	111 (20%)
Water source			
Improved	1,153 (83%)	713 (85%)	440 (79%)
Unimproved	244 (17%)	130 (15%)	114 (21%)
Type of toilet used by the household			
Flush toilet	135 (9.7%)	88 (10%)	47 (8.5%)
Pit latrine	1,209 (87%)	728 (86%)	481 (87%)

Characteristic	Overall, N = 1,398 ¹	AST Sample, N = 844 ¹	Not Sampled, N = 554 ¹
Other(bush/cat)	53 (3.8%)	28 (3.3%)	25 (4.5%)
Exclusive breastfeeding for first 6 months of life (or until enrollment if child <6 m)			
Never breastfed	24 (1.7%)	16 (1.9%)	8 (1.4%)
Exclusively breastfed	663 (47%)	397 (47%)	266 (48%)
Partially breastfed	632 (45%)	381 (45%)	251 (45%)
Unknown	79 (5.7%)	50 (5.9%)	29 (5.2%)
Acute malnutrition based on WLZ, MUAC (in 6+ month olds), and/or presence of edema			
None	1,266 (91%)	757 (90%)	509 (92%)
MAM	75 (5.4%)	44 (5.2%)	31 (5.6%)
SAM	57 (4.1%)	43 (5.1%)	14 (2.5%)
Child HIV status			
HIV unexposed	1,192 (85%)	722 (86%)	470 (85%)
HIV exposed, uninfected/infection status unknown	147 (11%)	85 (10%)	62 (11%)
HIV infected	18 (1.3%)	13 (1.5%)	5 (0.9%)
Uninfected/exposure status unknown	41 (2.9%)	24 (2.8%)	17 (3.1%)
Has recommended number of vaccines for this age (with grace of 4 weeks)			
No	96 (6.9%)	58 (6.9%)	38 (6.9%)
Yes	1,296 (93%)	783 (93%)	513 (93%)
Any antibiotic used during enrollment admission	1,253 (90%)	757 (90%)	496 (90%)
Any antibiotic prescribed at discharge	867 (62%)	530 (63%)	337 (61%)
Antibiotic use reported during the follow-up (considers missing as non-abx user)	312 (22%)	194 (23%)	118 (21%)
Child died during follow-up	34 (2.4%)	20 (2.4%)	14 (2.5%)
Child was rehospitalized at least once during follow-up	115 (8.2%)	71 (8.4%)	44 (7.9%)

¹n (%); Median (IQR)

Table S3. Per-protocol analysis results: Effect of azithromycin on the proportion of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistant to azithromycin at 3- and 6-months post-discharge among those who reported taking all five doses

Analysis	Timepoint	Azithromycin-treated		Placebo-treated		Adjusted Prevalence ratio (95% CI)
		n/N	%	n/N	%	
Per Protocol I*						
	Enrollment	14/97	14.4	17/102	16.7	0.92 (0.49, 1.75)
	Month 3	32/254	12.6	31/248	12.5	1.01 (0.63, 1.62)
	Month 6	38/237	16.0	38/233	16.3	1.06 (0.71, 1.59)
Per Protocol II**						
	Enrollment	8/49	16.3	8/40	20.0	0.82 (0.35, 1.96)
	Month 3	13/114	11.4	14/108	13.0	0.90 (0.44, 1.84)
	Month 6	20/101	19.8	15/106	14.2	1.43 (0.77, 2.65)

Prevalence ratio adjusted for county of enrollment

*includes only those who reported taking all 5 doses of study drug via adherence questionnaire

**includes only those who reported taking all 5 doses of study drug via bottle tick-mark

Figure S4. Distribution of doxycycline disc diffusion values at study enrollment (n=210 *S. pneumoniae* isolates)

Figure S5. Distribution of ceftriaxone MIC values at study enrollment (n=210 *S. pneumoniae* isolates)

Footnote:

*Intermediate for meningitis only. These isolates are susceptible by non-meningitis MIC break points ($\leq 1 \mu\text{g/mL}$)

Figure S6. The effect of azithromycin on the proportion of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistant to azithromycin, stratified by whether the child received any antibiotics during their hospitalization

Table S4. The effect of azithromycin on the proportion of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistant to azithromycin, stratified by whether the child received any antibiotics during their hospitalization

	Timepoint	Azithromycin-treated		Placebo-treated		Prevalence Ratio (95% CI), adjusted for county ¹	Prevalence Ratio (95% CI) adjusted for county and baseline resistance ²
		n/N	%	n/N	%		
No antibiotics during hospitalization	Enrollment	1/28	3.6	4/20	20.0	0.22 (0.03, 1.61)	0.37 (0.09, 1.51)
	Month 3	4/37	10.8	4/25	16.0	0.71 (0.19, 2.67)	1.33 (0.31, 5.66)
	Month 6	8/31	25.8	3/23	13.0	2.18 (0.67, 7.09)	5.4 (1.53, 19.1)
Antibiotics during hospitalization	Enrollment	14/76	18.4	14/86	16.3	1.17 (0.61, 2.27)	1.06 (0.74, 1.51)
	Month 3	31/229	13.5	28/231	12.1	1.12 (0.69, 1.80)	1.13 (0.71, 1.81)
	Month 6	33/214	15.4	40/220	18.2	0.91 (0.60, 1.38)	0.91 (0.60, 1.39)

¹GEE model, with Poisson link and exchangeable correlation structure, adjusted for enrollment county

²GEE model, with Poisson link and exchangeable correlation structure, adjusted for enrollment county and resistance to azithromycin at enrollment

Figure S7. The effect of azithromycin on the proportion of *S. pneumoniae* isolates resistant to azithromycin, stratified by enrollment county

